

Source: [Heravi, M.M.](#), Sadjadi, S., Nahavandi, F. (2015), Efficient synthesis of novel imidazo[1,2-a]pyrimidine derivatives via one-pot three-component procedure, Journal of Journal of the Iranian Chemical Society, 12(6), doi: [10.1007/s13738-014-0564-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13738-014-0564-x)

Efficient synthesis of novel imidazo[1,2-a]pyrimidine derivatives via one-pot three-component procedure

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Abstract

Synthesis of novel derivatives of imidazo[1,2-a]pyrimidine from one-pot three-component reaction of aldehydes, 2-amino-benzimidazole, and α -tetralone in the presence of catalytic amount of p-toluene sulfonic acid under reflux condition in EtOH has been presented. The simplicity and safety of the process, high yields and short reaction times were the main advantages of this protocol.

Keyword

Imidazo[12-a]pyrimidines, Multi-component reaction, One-pot reaction